

New Paradigm of Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) As an Effort To Combat Sea Piracy

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Abstract: *The writing of this scientific article is the result of an elaboration of studies; The Sociological Review of Sea Piracy Lecture and the 2020 National Maritime Day Commemoration Webinar in which the author participated. This scientific article uses a qualitative-descriptive method. To maintain focus in this scientific work, this paper is based on the Hierarchy of Needs Theory put forward by Maslow and the New Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) Paradigm Concept put forward by Octavian (2020). The author wants to describe that the New Paradigm of Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) can be proclaimed as an effort to minimize crimes committed. The key question to be answered in this article is how the New Paradigm of Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) can eradicate sea piracy crimes.*

Keywords: New Paradigm of Maritime Domain Awareness, Sea Piracy, Hierarchy of Needs

I. INTRODUCTION

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS 1982) has stated that sea piracy is one of the crimes at sea, so based on this, sea piracy is a threat to maritime security. Sea Piracy is defined as an act of entering a ship to commit theft or other crimes with the specific intention of using violence in carrying out ship piracy activities. The perpetrators of piracy, namely pirates, were social bandits at sea in the context of the south coast of China in the 15th century under the Ming empire (Moleenar, 2020). Moleenar (2020) mentions several main causes of rampant piracy in the context of China's southern coast in the 15th century due to poverty and hunger; socio-economic inequality in agrarian communities and fishing/coastal communities; the government's indifference to the development of coastal community life; state control; as well as dark figures of crime in society. In general, acts of piracy at sea were initially motivated by socioeconomic factors (Trianatha, 2017). In its development, the meaning of the phenomenon of emergence in the context of crime at sea is increasingly broadened. This is considering the increasing possibility of the threat of acts of terrorism against the background of non-economic (ideological) issues, where these actions may be carried out at sea, as well as on ships at sea.

Based on the expansion of the meaning of piracy in the context of crime at sea, the efforts made in alleviating and/or minimizing these actions also shift in a direction that is in line with the expansion of the meaning of piracy, so that later the efforts presented can be on target to resolve the problem. UNCLOS 1982 has regulated piracy contained in Articles 100 to Article 107. The main point of the discussion on piracy in UNCLOS 1982, is that piracy is an act of violence against the law to fulfill personal needs and goals (Vidianditha, Mangku, & Yuliartini, 2020). Regulations related to efforts to eradicate piracy are regulated both internationally and nationally (Latusia, 2021). In this scientific work, researchers want to echoing preventive efforts, which aim to prevent and minimize the occurrence of piracy crimes. The effort in this scientific article is the New Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) Paradigm, namely the expansion of the Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) paradigm, namely the reframing of the concept that originally MDA was synonymous with the use of technology related to sensing and information exchange to revamping the concept of non-physical sea power.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative-descriptive method. Qualitative research is research that is descriptive and uses stages of analysis. Process and meaning (subject perspective) are emphasized in qualitative research. The theoretical basis is

used as a guide so that the research focus is following the facts in the field. Qualitative data is data in the form of a narrative, in contrast to quantitative data in the form of numbers. In general, the qualitative data collected relates to influential social phenomena or symptoms in a group or community. A typical reaction when thinking about qualitative data collection is to focus on the actual types of data and their collection procedures (Sugiyono, 2010). This method is aimed at finding the facts and data needed after that is done by looking for problems that can find solutions to these problems (Waluyo, 2002).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Maritime Domain Awareness

Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) is the effective understanding of global maritime domains that may impact security, safety, the economy, or the environment. MDA is a key component of an active and deeply layered maritime defense. This is achieved by enhancing the ability to gather, collect, analyze, display, and disseminate actionable information and intelligence to operational commanders. MDA is supported by the Global Maritime Intelligence Integration Plan and is a backer of the Operational Maritime Threat Response Plan. Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) was originally developed by United States, which interests as a response to the September 11, 2001 attacks and terror attacks on the destroyer USS Cole (Boraz, 2009). Two factors are driving the development of MDA, namely: (1) political and security interests and (2) economic interests. Specifically, the USA initiatives related to MDA are:

- a. Proliferation Security Initiative;
- b. Regional Maritime Security Initiative;
- c. Global Threat Reduction Initiative;
- d. Container Security Initiative;
- e. Megaport Initiative;
- f. International Ship and Port Facility Security Initiative; as well as
- g. Aviation Safety Initiative.

These part conclusion is the initiative covers the physical strength of infrastructure. Apart from the American MDA perspective, there are other perspectives, namely the Chinese and Australian perspectives on MDA. MDA based on China's perspective uses political and economic instruments; So far government authorities have attempted to advance their interests at sea without resorting to the Armed Forces. A key element of Australia's MDA system is the Australian Maritime Identification System (AMIS), which was introduced in 2005 and is intended to provide awareness to the whole-of-government maritime domain across military and civil domains. It is a multi-level secure ocean surveillance system that identifies all data shipments available to Australian Federal agencies (Slocombe, 2021).

2. Hierarchy of Needs Theory by A. A. Maslow

Abraham Maslow put forward five human needs based on their level of importance starting from the lowest, namely physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, ego needs, and the highest need for self-actualization. According to Maslow's theory, humans try to meet lower-level needs first before meeting higher needs. Consumers who have been able to fulfill their basic needs, then other higher needs usually appear, and so on (Sumarwan, 2011). Abraham Maslow, a clinical psychologist, introduced a tiered theory of needs known as Maslow's theory or the Hierarchy of Human Needs, which proposed five human needs based on their level of importance. Humans try to meet the needs of the lowest level, namely physiological needs, then they will level up after the previous needs have been met, and so on until they reach the highest need, namely self-actualization (Sumarwan, 2011). Physiological Needs Are basic human needs, namely the needs of the human body to sustain life. These needs include food, air, housing, clothing, and sex. Safety needs are the second level needs after basic needs. This is a need for protection for the human body. Humans need protection from criminal disturbances so that they can live safely and comfortably. Social Needs these are needs based on a sense of being owned so that they can be accepted by the people around them or their environment. These needs are based on the need for humans to relate to one another. Ego Needs Are the need to achieve a higher degree than others. Humans seek to achieve prestige, reputation, and better status. Humans have a strong ego to be able to achieve better achievements for themselves and better than others. Self-Actualization Needs This is a need that is based on the desire of an individual to make himself the best person

according to his potential and abilities. An individual needs to express himself in an activity to prove himself that he is capable of doing that.

3. New Paradigm Concept of Maritime Domain Awareness

Octavian (2020) mentions that a sea is a meeting place for the interests of various parties, both in terms of cooperation and conflict. HastoKristiyanto also emphasized that the sea is the front page of a nation. In the economic field, the sea is a place for interests, both exploitation of natural resources and trade crossings. The problem is that often a nation pays less attention to understanding the situation and conditions of maritime reality. Octavian said that so far MDA has been synonymous with the use of technology related to sensing and the exchange of information. However, when expanding the meaning and concept of MDA, there is another side of MDA that requires non-physical "improvement". What is meant is of course the perspective of looking at the maritime sector from all maritime stakeholders. MDA, which was originally aimed solely at guaranteeing security from all forms of maritime security threats, is also aimed at safety and protection (Octavian, 2020). The objectives of safety and protection in the maritime sector, in essence, contain efforts to:

- a. Harmonization of maritime sector regulations related to violations and/or crimes that occur at sea;
- b. Strengthening stakeholders' awareness of maritime institutional governance; and
- c. Management of marine space and protection of the marine environment.

4. New Paradigm of Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) as an Effort to Combat Sea Piracy

From the previous description of the main causes of piracy, then basically piracy occurs because the basic needs of individuals are not fulfilled, this is in line with the Hierarchy of Needs Theory put forward by Maslow seeing that individuals have stages of basic needs that they want to achieve. The main needs that are not met in individual pirates are physiological needs; because the needs of the stomach encourage them to justify any means to fill their stomach. The reality is that pirates not only support themselves personally but in some cases, they are a 'backbone' for their family; therefore the stronger his conviction to justify the crime he committed. The eradication of the phenomenon of piracy can use several alternative approaches, one of which is a social approach using both formal and informal institutions in society, such as (Yulianto, 2022):

- a. Understand the historical roots, social structures, and social conflicts between maritime communities and between countries which are mainly based on the sea area and the marine potential contained therein; so as to provide an understanding of the social phenomenon of piracy.
- b. Understand the concept of economic empowerment that can be rolled out to the maritime community; so as to create appropriate maritime-based economic facilities and infrastructure.
- c. Understand the rationale of the maritime management regime implemented by several countries; so as to develop alternative jobs that can overcome the problem of unemployment.
- d. Understanding ideas or ideas on how to build aspects of the country's maritime defense by involving/participating in the maritime community.

The phenomenon of piracy that is studied sociologically tends to be discussed in the preventive realm or that is preventing the reduction of acts of piracy. But nowadays, because the phenomenon of piracy has occurred in many parts of the world, especially in strategic countries; then the next approach that the author wants to review is the security approach. Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) is a national plan with global coverage designed to deal with current and future maritime security challenges (Sumakul, 2020). So far, MDA is synonymous with the use of technology related to sensing and information exchange; however, we have to look at MDA from another perspective, namely MDA which is non-physical in nature or can be called the New Paradigm of Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA). The keyword for MDA is awareness, which means that all parties with an interest in what is happening in the maritime domain require awareness. The problem of awareness is not only related to hardware, but also the paradigm of all maritime stakeholders. The new MDA paradigm is an improvement on the paradigm that originally MDA was aimed solely at guaranteeing security from all forms of maritime security threats, increasing by aiming at safety and protection (Octavian, 2020). Based on the explanation above, the New Paradigm of MDA plays a major role in alleviating piracy crimes. All stakeholders are expected to be able to pay attention to achieving security, safety, and protection in the maritime domain. Vigilance in the maritime domain in combating piracy can be built based on the results of the study of the sociological approach above (re: paragraph one). The

implementation of the New Paradigm of MDA in alleviating piracy can be started with (Octavian, New Paradigm of Maritime Domain Awareness Indonesia, 2020):

- a. Building Awareness: MDA was built to realize the level of awareness of the whole nation to understand the situation and condition of the character of the people in which we live and lead a life of maritime realities. Awareness is needed to carry out internal reforms in the basic life of a nation to recognize identity as a maritime nation which is an external manifestation in mindset, attitude patterns, and behavior patterns that are very significant in the life of the nation and state.
- b. Building Understanding: Understanding MDA at the extrapolation level so that a nation can project MDA awareness to see far-sighted visions as well as implications, consequences, and risks in its efforts to achieve prosperity and prosperity for the entire community due to the abundance of sea blessings.
- c. Building Vigilance: in line with national awareness, MDA awareness is directed at increasing the ability of early detection and deterrence to overcome all forms of Threats, Challenges, Obstacles, and Disturbances (ATHG) to national interests over the sea and air space above the sea.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the maritime security discipline, the main issues are threats and security in the maritime field. Existing threats must be resolved, to find a solution. In short, the social and security approach in conducting a review of piracy is to discuss the origins of piracy, social interaction, social dynamics, and stakeholders. In national security and maritime security, society is the subject of the embodiment of the security dimension, therefore building awareness and capabilities of the maritime community itself is the key to sustainable development in the maritime sector, to make maritime culture grounded in the country. The context of problems and social phenomena must be preceded by an in-depth analysis so that good quality regarding maritime policy is a necessity that can be applied in general.

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